

Figure Z6

Figure Z6: Original cell type annotation and marker gene expression for a single-cell mouse subcutaneous white adipose tissue study. (A) Single-cell clustering of 89,434 cells in GSE133486. The UMAP plot is coloured by original cell type annotation provided by the authors. MA, mature adipocyte; APC, adipose progenitor cell; Dend, dendritic cell; Macro, macrophage; Neu, neutrophil; Endo, endothelial cell; Div, dividing cell; Eryth, erythrocyte; Ukn, unknown. **(B-F)** Marker gene expression for adipose stem cell **(B)**, T-cell **(C)**, macrophage **(D)**, and other major cell types **(E)**. Cell clusters with uncertain marker gene expression are boxed. A list of abbreviations used in this figure appear in the Methods.